

Analysis of The Influence of Organizational Climate, Job Promotion and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance at The Medan Barat Primary Tax Service Office in 2024

Jeffrany¹, Hendra Rahayu², Baharuddin³, Junaidi⁴, Ikhwanul Fitra⁵, Eddy Suprayitno^{6*}

^{1,2,3,4,5,6}Management, Universitas Islam Sumatera Utara, Medan City, Indonesia

Article DOI: [10.55677/SSHRB/2025-3050-0602](https://doi.org/10.55677/SSHRB/2025-3050-0602)

DOI URL: <https://doi.org/10.55677/SSHRB/2025-3050-0602>

KEYWORDS: Organizational Climate, Job Promotion, Job Satisfaction, Employee Performance, Tax Service Office

ABSTRACT: This study aims to analyze the influence of organizational climate, job promotion, and job satisfaction on employee performance at the Medan Barat Pratama Tax Service Office, both partially and simultaneously. The objects of this research are: organizational climate, job promotion and job satisfaction as independent variables and employee performance as the dependent variable. The research was conducted at the Medan Barat Pratama Tax Service Office located at Jalan Asrama Number 7A, Sei Sikambing C. II, Medan Helvetia District, Medan City, North Sumatra Province. The research process was carried out and completed in August to October 2024. Data collection methods used include interviews, questionnaires, and documentation. Data analysis techniques are carried out by multiple regression analysis using the IMB Statistik for Product and Service Solution (SPSS) version 24 program. The population used is 113 employees and the research sample is 53 people. The results of the study indicate that organizational climate does not have a significant effect on employee performance, as indicated by the results of the t-test with t count $< t$ table ($1.452 < 2.010$) at a significance level of 95%. On the other hand, job promotion has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, with t count $> t$ table ($5.823 > 2.010$). Job satisfaction also has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, which is supported by t count $> t$ table ($2.252 > 2.010$). Simultaneously, organizational climate, job promotion, and job satisfaction have a positive and significant effect on employee performance, as evidenced by the F count $> F$ table ($30.169 > 2.79$). Based on the results of this study, it can be concluded that although organizational climate does not have a significant influence on employee performance, job promotion and job satisfaction play an important role in improving employee performance at the Medan Barat Pratama Tax Service Office. Thus, the research hypothesis is accepted.

Corresponding Author:
Eddy Suprayitno

Published: June 09, 2025

License: This is an open access article under the CC BY 4.0 license:
<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

1. INTRODUCTION

Employee performance is one of the main factors that determine the success of an organization, including the Tax Service Office (KPP). Optimal employee performance will contribute to increasing the efficiency and effectiveness of tax services, which ultimately supports the achievement of state revenue targets (Wibowo & Murwaningsari, 2024). However, achieving good performance cannot be separated from various influencing factors, such as organizational climate, job promotion, and job satisfaction (Raziq & Maulabakhsh, 2015).

Organizational climate reflects the conditions of the work environment felt by employees, both in terms of policy, work culture, and relationships between employees (James et al., 2008; Schneider et al., 2013; Pawirosumarto et al., 2017). A positive organizational climate can create a conducive work atmosphere, increase motivation, and encourage employee productivity (Tsai et al., 2015; Sadewo et al., 2021). Conversely, an unsupportive work climate can hinder performance and reduce employee morale.

Employee performance plays a very important role in determining the effectiveness of an organization, including the Tax Service Office (KPP). Optimal employee performance not only ensures that tax services run smoothly, but also contributes to the

achievement of state revenue targets. Employees who have high performance will be able to carry out their duties more efficiently and provide quality services to taxpayers. This efficiency has an impact on increasing public compliance in paying taxes, which ultimately supports the stability of state finances.

However, employee performance achievement does not just happen, but is influenced by various internal and external factors (Barera, 2023). One factor that plays an important role is organizational climate (Schneider et al., 2011; Schneider et al., 2013). Organizational climate reflects the conditions of the work environment felt by employees in their daily lives (Berman Brown & Brooks, 2002; De Clercq & Rius, 2007). Aspects such as organizational policies, work culture, and relationships between employees and superiors can shape employee perceptions of their workplace (Harter et al., 2010).

If the organizational climate in an agency is positive—for example, there is open communication, fair policies, and harmonious working relationships—then employees will feel comfortable and motivated to work better. They will be more productive, have high work enthusiasm, and be able to carry out their duties with full responsibility. Conversely, if the organizational climate is less supportive, for example there is unclear policy, lack of appreciation from leaders, or less harmonious relationships between employees, then employees will feel less comfortable. As a result, work motivation decreases, productivity decreases, and the quality of services provided can also be affected.

Thus, understanding and creating a conducive organizational climate is an important step for the Tax Service Office to ensure that employees can work optimally. Leaders need to take strategic steps in building a healthy work atmosphere, creating transparent and fair policies, and encouraging good working relationships among all employees. With a supportive work environment, employees will be more enthusiastic in carrying out their duties, so that the efficiency and effectiveness of tax services can increase significantly. Previous research was conducted by Pasaribu & Indrawati (2016) entitled *Pengaruh Iklim Organisasi dan Kualitas Kehidupan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Dinas Sosial Provinsi Bali* (The Influence of Organizational Climate and Quality of Work Life on the Performance of Employees of the Bali Provincial Social Service), the results of the study showed that organizational climate has a positive influence on employee performance at the Bali Provincial Social Service.

In addition to organizational climate, job promotions also play a role in improving employee performance. The opportunity to get a promotion creates motivation for employees to work better, improve their competence, and show dedication in their work. Promotions that are carried out fairly and transparently will increase employee morale and strengthen loyalty to the organization. Anggini (2022) conducted a study entitled *Pengaruh Promosi dan Beban Kerja Terhadap Kepuasan Kerja Pegawai Perum Perhutani Divre III Jawa Barat dan Banten* (The Effect of Job Promotion and Training on Employee Performance at Perum Perhutani HR and General Affairs Unit III West Java & Banten), the results of the study stated that job promotions together have a positive effect on employee performance at Perum Perhutani HR and General Affairs Unit III West Java & Banten.

Another factor that is no less important is job satisfaction. Employees who are satisfied with their jobs tend to have higher motivation and work more optimally. Job satisfaction can be influenced by various aspects, such as the compensation system, work environment, relationships with superiors and coworkers, and career development opportunities. A high level of satisfaction will have an impact on increasing productivity and individual and organizational performance as a whole.

Yurasti (2018) conducted a study entitled *Pengaruh Kompensasi dan Kepuasan Kerja terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Dinas Pertanian Tanaman Pangan Hortikultura dan Peternakan Kabupaten Pasaman Barat* (The Influence of Compensation and Job Satisfaction on the Performance of Employees of the Agriculture, Food Crops, Horticulture and Livestock Service of West Pasaman Regency). The results of the study stated that Job Satisfaction had a significant effect on the Performance of Employees of the Agriculture, Food Crops, Horticulture and Livestock Service of West Pasaman Regency. Based on this background, this study aims to analyze the influence of organizational climate, job promotion, and job satisfaction on employee performance at the Tax Service Office. This study is expected to provide deeper insight into the factors that contribute to improving employee performance and provide recommendations for organizations in managing human resources more effectively.

2. METHODOLOGY

This research was conducted at the Medan Barat Pratama Tax Service Office located at Jalan Asrama Number 7A, Sei Sikambang C. II, Medan Helvetia District, Medan City, North Sumatra Province. The objects of this research are: organizational climate, job promotion and job satisfaction as independent variables and employee performance as the dependent variable. The population in this study were all employees of the Medan Barat Pratama Tax Service Office, 113 people. The population in this study was 113 and the precision set or significance level was 0.1, so the sample size in this study was:

$$n = \frac{113}{113 \cdot 0,1^2 + 1}$$

Operational definition can be based on one or more references accompanied by the reasons for using the definition. In this study, the author identified two research variables, namely:

1. Independent variable

According to Rubiyanto (2013:24), the independent variable is a variable that is intentionally carried out by action that will be measured for the intensity of its influence on its contribution to the dependent variable. The independent variables in this study are stated as X (Organizational climate (X1), Job promotion (X2) and Job satisfaction (X3).

2. Dependent variable

According to Rubiyanto (2013:25) the dependent variable is a variable whose existence is determined by the independent variable. In this study, the independent variable studied is stated as Y (Employee Performance).

In this study, the data analysis technique used is multiple linear regression analysis and uses a tool in the form of SPSS computer software. SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) is a computer program used to analyze data with statistical analysis, the SPSS used in this study is SPSS version 24. The data analysis technique used in this study is descriptive analysis and multiple regression analysis. In this study, the data model uses multiple regression analysis. Regression analysis is used for forecasting purposes, where in the model there is a dependent and independent variable.

The multiple linear regression equation in this study is as follows:

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + e$$

Partial Significance Test (t-Test)

The steps in decision making for the t-test are to look at the significant value, if the sig α value < 0.05 then it can be concluded that the independent variable partially has a significant effect on the dependent variable or the hypothesis is accepted. Likewise, if the sig α value > 0.05 then it can be concluded that the independent variable partially does not have a significant effect on the dependent variable or the hypothesis is rejected, Ghozali (2016:97).

With the decision-making rules:

H0: $b_1, b_2, b_3 = 0$ (organizational climate, job promotion and job satisfaction partially do not affect employee performance at the Medan Barat Pratama Tax Service Office).

H1: $b_1, b_2, b_3 \neq 0$ (organizational climate, job promotion and job satisfaction partially affect employee performance at the t Medan Barat Pratama Tax Service Office).

The t-test is conducted to determine whether the independent variable partially has a significant effect on the dependent variable. In this case, t_{count} is compared with t_{table} with the following conditions: If the value of $t_{count} < t_{table}$ then H0 is accepted and H1 is rejected, at α 5%. This means that the independent variables partially do not have a significant effect on the dependent variable. If the value of $t_{count} > t_{table}$ then H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted, at α 5%. This means that the independent variables partially have a significant effect on the dependent variables.

Simultaneous Significance Test (F Test)

The steps in decision making for the F test are to look at the significant value, if the sig α value < 0.05 then it can be concluded that the independent variables simultaneously or together have a significant effect on the dependent variable or the hypothesis is accepted. Likewise, if the sig α value > 0.05 then it can be concluded that the independent variables simultaneously or together do not have a significant effect on the dependent variable or the hypothesis is rejected, (Ghozali, 2016:96) with the decision-making rules:

H0: $b_1, b_2, b_3 = 0$ (organizational climate, job promotion and job satisfaction simultaneously do not affect employee performance at the Medan Barat Pratama Tax Service Office).

H1: $b_1, b_2, b_3 \neq 0$ (organizational climate, job promotion and job satisfaction simultaneously affect employee performance at the Medan Barat Pratama Tax Service Office).

If $F_{count} < F_{table}$, then H0 is accepted and H1 is rejected, at $\alpha = 5\%$. This means that the independent variables simultaneously do not have a significant effect on the dependent variable. If $F_{count} > F_{table}$, then H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted, at $\alpha = 5\%$. This means that the independent variables simultaneously have a significant effect on the dependent variable.

Coefficient of Determination Test

The Coefficient of Determination (r^2) is intended to measure the ability of how much percentage of independent variables in the multiple regression model in explaining the dependent variable. The value of the coefficient of determination is between 0 and 1. A small r^2 value means that the ability of the independent variables in explaining the variation of the dependent variable is very limited. A value close to 1 means that the independent variables provide almost all the information needed to predict the dependent variable.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data Quality Test

Validity

Instrument validity testing can be seen in the Corrected Item-Total Correlation column. If the correlation number obtained is greater than the critical number ($r\text{-count} > r\text{-table}$) then the instrument is said to be valid. based on the validity test, it can be concluded that all question items to measure each research variable are declared valid. The results of the variable validity test are as follows.

Table 1. Variable Validity Test

Variables	Instrument	r-count	r-table	Information
Organizational climate (X1)	1) IO1	0.498	0.270	Valid
	2) IO2	0.449	0.270	Valid
	3) IO3	0.427	0.270	Valid
	4) IO4	0.284	0.270	Valid
	5) IO5	0.368	0.270	Valid
	6) IO6	0.597	0.270	Valid
	7) IO7	0.651	0.270	Valid
	8) IO8	0.403	0.270	Valid
	9) IO9	0.508	0.270	Valid
	10) IO10	0.498	0.270	Valid
Job promotion (X2)	1) PJ1	0.295	0.270	Valid
	2) PJ2	0.596	0.270	Valid
	3) PJ3	0.617	0.270	Valid
	4) PJ4	0.491	0.270	Valid
	5) PJ5	0.516	0.270	Valid
	6) PJ6	0.618	0.270	Valid
	7) PJ7	0.648	0.270	Valid
	8) PJ8	0.606	0.270	Valid
	9) PJ9	0.691	0.270	Valid
	10) PJ10	0.519	0.270	Valid
Job satisfaction (X3)	1) KK1	0.556	0.270	Valid
	2) KK2	0.387	0.270	Valid
	3) KK3	0.529	0.270	Valid
	4) KK4	0.565	0.270	Valid
	5) KK5	0.612	0.270	Valid
	6) KK6	0.674	0.270	Valid
	7) KK7	0.640	0.270	Valid
	8) KK8	0.720	0.270	Valid
	9) KK9	0.486	0.270	Valid
	10) KK10	0.491	0.270	Valid
Employee Performance (Y)	1) KP1	0.654	0.270	Valid
	2) KP2	0.689	0.270	Valid
	3) KP3	0.757	0.270	Valid
	4) KP4	0.541	0.270	Valid
	5) KP5	0.749	0.270	Valid
	6) KP6	0.764	0.270	Valid
	7) KP7	0.783	0.270	Valid
	8) KP8	0.527	0.270	Valid
	9) KP9	0.451	0.270	Valid
	10) KP10	0.559	0.270	Valid

Source: Research Results 2024

Reliability

After conducting a validity test, the next step is to conduct a data reliability test to determine whether the instrument is reliable by looking at the Cronbach's Alpha value. Reliability testing is carried out to determine whether the measuring instrument used is

reliable and remains consistent if the measurement is repeated. A questionnaire is said to be reliable if Cronbach's Alpha is greater than 0.6. This indicates that the research data is declared reliable.

Table 2. Variable Reliability Test

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	Reliability Limits	Information
Organizational climate (X1)	0.677	0.6	Reliable
Job promotion (X2)	0.725	0.6	Reliable
Job satisfaction (X3)	0.739	0.6	Reliable
Employee performance (Y)	0.743	0.6	Reliable

Source: Research Results 2024

From the data in table 2 above, it can be seen that the results of the reliability test calculations show that the Cronbach's alpha in each variable column is greater than 0.6 (reliability limit), so the instrument can be stated as reliable.

Classical Assumption Test

1. Normality Test

Fig. 1. Data Normality Test Graph

Based on Figure 1 above, it can be seen that the data is spread around the diagonal line and follows the direction of the diagonal line on the histogram graph, this indicates that the distribution pattern is normal. So it can be concluded that based on the P-P plot graph, the regression model meets the assumption of normality.

2. Multicollinearity Test

Table 3. Multicollinearity Test

Coefficients ^a		Collinearity Statistics	
Model		Tolerance	VIF
1	Organizational Climate	.885	1.130
	Job Promotion	.677	1.477
	Job satisfaction	.671	1.491

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

Source: Research Results 2024

Looking at the results of the tolerance value shows that no independent variables have a tolerance value of less than 0.10, which means there is no correlation between independent variables or there is no multicollinearity. The results of the calculation of the variance inflation factor (VIF) value also show the same thing, no independent variable has a VIF value of more than 10. So, it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity between independent variables in the regression model.

3. Heteroscedasticity Test

The heteroscedasticity assumption test concludes that the regression model does not experience heteroscedasticity. In other words, there is equality of variance from residuals from one observation to another. The results of the heteroscedasticity test can be seen in Figure 2 below:

Fig. 2. Heteroscedasticity Test

Hypothesis Testing

1. Hypothesis Testing with t-Test

Hypothesis testing with t-test, namely by observing the calculated t value from the regression results to determine the effect of the independent variable partially on the dependent variable with a significance level in this study using alpha 5% or 0.05. The value of the calculated t-test can be seen from the p-value (in the Sig. column) on each independent variable, if the p-value is smaller than the specified level of significance or the calculated t (in the t column) is greater than the t table (calculated from two-tailed $\alpha = 5\%$ df-k, k is the number of independent variables), then the value of the independent variable partially has a significant effect on the dependent variable (in the sense that H_a is accepted and H_o is rejected, in other words, there is an influence between the independent variable and the dependent variable).

The method for determining the t table uses a significance level of 5%, with $df = n - k - 1$ (in this study $df = 53 - 4 - 1 = 48$), so that the t table value is 2.010 presented in table 3 as follows:

Table 4. Partial Test (t-Test)

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	2.078	5.396		.385	.702
	Organizational Climate	.161	.111	.131	1.452	.153
	Job Promotion	.661	.113	.599	5.823	.000
	Job Satisfaction	.242	.107	.233	2.252	.029

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

Source: Data processed 2024

Based on the table above, it is known that the t-value of each independent variable partially affects the dependent variable, namely:

- a) The organizational climate variable has a p-value (in the Sig. column) of 0.153 <0.05, meaning it is not significant, while the t-value is 1.452 <from the t table of 2.010, meaning it is not significant. This means that the organizational climate does not affect employee performance.
- b) The job promotion variable has a p-value (in the Sig. column) of 0.000 <0.05, meaning it is significant, while the t-value is 5.823 > from the t table of 2.010, meaning it is significant. This means that job promotion has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

- c) The job satisfaction variable has a p-value (in the Sig. column) of 0.029 <0.05, meaning it is significant, while the t-value is 2.252 > from the t table of 2.010, meaning it is significant. This means that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

2. Hypothesis Testing with F Test

The results of the F test show that the independent variables simultaneously influence the dependent variable, if the p-value (in the sig. column) is smaller than the specified level of significance (5%), or the calculated F (in the F column) is greater than the F table. The F table is calculated using $df1 = k-1$, and $df2 = n - k$, namely $df1 = 4 - 1 = 3$ and $df2 = 53 - 4 = 49$, so that the F table value is 2.79. Meanwhile, the results of the F test with the help of the SPSS program can be seen in the table below:

Table 5. Simultaneous Test Results (F Test)

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	345.093	3	115.031	30.169	.000 ^b
	Residual	186.832	49	3.813		
	Total	531.925	52			

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Job Satisfaction, Organizational Climate, Job Promotion

Source: Data processed 2024

Based on the F test or Anova test or simultaneous test above, the calculated F is 30.169 at $\alpha = 5\%$ or 0.05 with a significant level of 0.000 because the probability value (0.000) is much smaller than 0.05, so the regression model can be used to predict that organizational climate (X1), job promotion (X2), and job satisfaction (X3) as independent variables simultaneously affect employee performance (Y). In other words, organizational climate (X1), job promotion (X2), and job satisfaction (X3) simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on employee performance, because the calculated $F > F$ table, namely $30.169 > 2.79$. This means that if organizational climate (X1), job promotion (X2), and job satisfaction (X3) are jointly implemented in the organization, they will have an impact on increasing employee performance (Y). Conversely, if organizational climate (X1), job promotion (X2), and job satisfaction (X3) are not jointly implemented, they will have an impact on decreasing employee performance (Y).

3. Analysis of the Determination Coefficient (R²)

The R Square/Adjusted R Square value is said to be good if it is above 0.5 because the R Square value ranges from 0 to 1. The results of the determination coefficient analysis in this study can be seen in the following:

Table 6. Results of Determination Coefficient Analysis

Model Summary					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.805 ^a	.649	.627		1.953

a. Predictors: (Constant), Job Satisfaction, Organizational Climate, Job Promotion

Source: Data processed 2024

The processed results in the table above show the adjusted determination coefficient (R²) value (Adjusted R Square) of 0.649. This means that 64.9% of the dependent variable (employee performance) is influenced or explained by the independent variables, namely organizational climate, job promotion and job satisfaction and the remaining 35.1% (100% - 64.9%) is influenced or explained by other variables outside the variables used in this study.

Regression Equation Results

To facilitate the reading of the results and interpretation of the regression analysis, the equation form is used. The equation or model contains constants and regression coefficients obtained from the results of data processing that has been carried out previously.

Table 7. Multiple Linear Regression Test

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.078	5.396		.385	.702
	Organizational Climate	.161	.111	.131	1.452	.153
	Job Promotion	.661	.113	.599	5.823	.000
	Job Satisfaction	.242	.107	.233	2.252	.029

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

Source: Data processed 2024

The regression equation that has been formulated is processed using data to obtain the final equation, namely:
 $Y = 2,078 + 0,161X_1 + 0,661X_2 + 0,242X_3$

In this regression model, the constant value listed as 2.078 can be interpreted if the independent variables in the model are assumed to be equal to zero or the independent variables in this case organizational climate, job promotion and job satisfaction are applied, then employee performance will increase by 2.078 units.

The value of the regression coefficient β_1 of 0.161 in this study can be interpreted that the organizational climate variable (X1) has no effect on employee performance (Y). This shows that when the organizational climate is met, employee performance will not increase by 0.161 units.

The value of the regression coefficient β_2 of 0.661 in this study can be interpreted that the job promotion variable (X2) has an effect on employee performance (Y). This shows that when the job promotion variable is met, employee performance will increase by 0.661 units.

The value of the regression coefficient β_3 of 0.242 in this study can be interpreted that the job satisfaction variable (X3) has an effect on employee performance (Y). This shows that when the job satisfaction variable is met, employee performance will increase by 0.242 units.

4. CONCLUSION

This study aims to see the influence of organizational climate, job promotion and job satisfaction on employee performance both simultaneously and partially. The results of this study provide the following conclusions:

1. Organizational climate partially does not affect employee performance at the Medan Barat Pratama Tax Service Office, this is supported by the results of the t-count analysis <t-table (1.452 <2.010) at n = 53 at a significance level of 95%.
2. Job promotion partially has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Medan Barat Pratama Tax Service Office, this is supported by the results of the t-count analysis > t-table (5.823 > 2.010) at n = 53 at a significance level of 95%.
3. Job satisfaction partially has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Medan Barat Pratama Tax Service Office, this is supported by the results of the t-count analysis > t-table (2.252 > 2.010) at n = 53 at a significance level of 95%.
4. Organizational climate, job promotion and job satisfaction simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Medan Barat Pratama Tax Service Office, this is supported by the results of the F-count analysis > F-table (30.169 > 2.79) at n = 53 at a significance level of 95%.

Based on the conclusions in this study, several suggestions can be put forward as follows: 1) The Medan Barat Pratama Tax Service Office is advised to carry out job promotions in accordance with procedures, honestly, fairly, and impartially. In its implementation, job promotions must pay attention to and refer to the employee's term of office, educational background, experience, abilities, and skills possessed by the employee. Promotion also provides employees with the same opportunity to get a promotion and get clarity on their career in the company so that job satisfaction is achieved; 2) The Medan Barat Pratama Tax Service Office to involve employees in decision making or provide opportunities for employees for important work so that employees feel they play an active role for the company and are challenged to complete it; 3) For further researchers, research can be conducted by expanding the

scope of research objects by examining variables that affect employee performance and increasing the research period so that maximum results can be obtained.

REFERENCES

1. Anggini, D. P. (2022). *PENGARUH PROMOSI DAN BEBAN KERJA TERHADAP KEPUASAN KERJA PEGAWAI PERUM PERHUTANI DIVRE III JAWA BARAT DAN BANTEN* [Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia]. https://repository.upi.edu/84212/1/S_MBS_1702592_Title.pdf
2. Barera, B. E. E. (2023). Factors Affecting the Achievement of Company Goals by Maximising Company Profits through Internal and External Factors. *Journal of Contemporary Administration and Management (ADMAN)*, 1(1), 17–21. <https://doi.org/10.61100/adman.v1i1.5>
3. Berman Brown, R., & Brooks, I. (2002). Emotion at work. *Journal of Management in Medicine*, 16(5), 327–344. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02689230210446517>
4. De Clercq, D., & Rius, I. B. (2007). Organizational Commitment in Mexican Small and Medium-Sized Firms: The Role of Work Status, Organizational Climate, and Entrepreneurial Orientation. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 45(4), 467–490. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-627X.2007.00223.x>
5. Ghozali, I. (2016). *Aplikasi Analisis Multivariete Dengan Program IBM SPSS 23* (8th ed.). Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
6. Harter, J. K., Schmidt, F. L., Asplund, J. W., Killham, E. A., & Agrawal, S. (2010). Causal Impact of Employee Work Perceptions on the Bottom Line of Organizations. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 5(4), 378–389. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1745691610374589>
7. James, L. R., Choi, C. C., Ko, C.-H. E., McNeil, P. K., Minton, M. K., Wright, M. A., & Kim, K. (2008). Organizational and psychological climate: A review of theory and research. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 17(1), 5–32. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13594320701662550>
8. Pasaribu, E. K., & Indrawati, A. D. (2016). PENGARUH IKLIM ORGANISASI DAN KUALITAS KEHIDUPAN KERJA TERHADAP KINERJA PEGAWAI DINAS SOSIAL PROVINSI BALI. *E-Jurnal Manajemen*, 5(12), 7785–7809. <https://ojs.unud.ac.id/index.php/manajemen/article/view/25306>
9. Pawirosumarto, S., Sarjana, P. K., & Gunawan, R. (2017). The effect of work environment, leadership style, and organizational culture towards job satisfaction and its implication towards employee performance in Parador Hotels and Resorts, Indonesia. *International Journal of Law and Management*, 59(6), 1337–1358. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJLMA-10-2016-0085>
10. Raziq, A., & Maulabakhsh, R. (2015). Impact of Working Environment on Job Satisfaction. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 23, 717–725. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671\(15\)00524-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671(15)00524-9)
11. Rubiyanto, R. (2013). *Metode Penelitian Pendidikan*. Universitas Muhammadiyah Surakarta.
12. Sadewo, I. P., Surachman, S., & Rofiaty, R. (2021). The influence of working environment to employee performance mediated by work motivation. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science (2147- 4478)*, 10(3), 213–222. <https://doi.org/10.20525/ijrbs.v10i3.1112>
13. Schneider, B., Ehrhart, M. G., & Macey, W. H. (2011). Perspectives on organizational climate and culture. In *APA handbook of industrial and organizational psychology, Vol 1: Building and developing the organization*. (pp. 373–414). American Psychological Association. <https://doi.org/10.1037/12169-012>
14. Schneider, B., Ehrhart, M. G., & Macey, W. H. (2013). Organizational Climate and Culture. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 64(1), 361–388. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-psych-113011-143809>
15. Tsai, C.-Y., Horng, J.-S., Liu, C.-H., & Hu, D.-C. (2015). Work environment and atmosphere: The role of organizational support in the creativity performance of tourism and hospitality organizations. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 46, 26–35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2015.01.009>
16. Wibowo, P., & Murwaningsari, E. (2024). Factors influencing non-tax revenue sustainability in Indonesian government institutions: the mediating role of accountability. *Cogent Business & Management*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2024.2303788>
17. Yurasti. (2018). PENGARUH KOMPENSASI DAN KEPUASAN KERJA TERHADAP KINERJA PEGAWAI DINAS PERTANIAN TANAMAN PANGAN HOLTIKULTURA DAN PETERNAKAN KABUPATEN PASAMAN BARAT. *Jurnal Apresiasi Ekonomi*, 5(1), 41–46. <https://doi.org/10.31846/jae.v5i1.125>